

FREQUENCY OF COMMON SITES OF VASCULAR LESIONS IN ORAL CAVITY AMONG PATIENTS PRESENTING TO KHYBER COLLEGE OF DENTISTRY

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Abstract

Background

Vascular lesions of the oral cavity are diverse in nature and vary in clinical presentation, anatomical location, and underlying pathology. Accurate identification of their frequency and distribution is essential for effective diagnosis and management. To determine the prevalence and distribution of various types of oral cavity vascular lesions in a sample of patients attending the Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery at Khyber College of Dentistry.

Methods

This six-month cross-sectional study included 80 individuals with clinically or radiologically confirmed vascular lesions in the oral cavity. Demographic and clinical data were recorded on a structured proforma. Superficial lesions were diagnosed clinically, while deep lesions were confirmed with imaging or histopathology. SPSS version 22 was utilized in the analysis. Categorical variables were also estimated in terms of frequencies and percentages, with age represented as an average and standard deviation. Associations were found using chi-square and Fisher's exact measures, with p-values less than 0.05 indicating significance.

Results

The patients had an average age of 22.13 ± 11.60 years and were slightly more in female (53.75%). Vascular malformation (56.3%) was identified as the most common type of lesion, followed by pyogenic granuloma (31.3%) and hemangioma (12.5%). The buccal mucosa was the most involved area (28.8%), with the mandible and maxilla being the least affected. In stratified analysis, there was a significant correlation between mandibular involvement and lesion type ($p = 0.0416$), and between age group and involvement of both buccal mucosa ($p = 0.0379$) and mandible ($p = 0.0129$).

Conclusion

The most common type of oral vascular lesion is with the buccal mucosa being the most frequently affected site. Age and lesion type were identified as key factors influencing lesion distribution. These findings highlight the importance of age- and location-dependent evaluation in clinical diagnosis and treatment planning.

INTRODUCTION

Vascular lesions include conditions that result in an abnormal position, structure and number of blood vessels. Vascular lesions can be categorized into two main types: vascular tumors and vascular malformations. Vascular tumors are endothelial neoplasms characterized by increased cellular proliferation and growth. On the other hand, vascular malformations result from the abnormal development of vascular elements during embryogenesis (1). Vascular tumors include hemangioma, kaposiform hemangioendothelioma, tufted angioma, and pyogenic granuloma (2).

The most common vascular tumors are hemangiomas (1). Lips is the common site of involvement 70% followed by the tongue 16% (3). Hemangiomas develop after birth and disappear over the years. Arteriovenous malformation results in obvious destruction and functional disability (4).

Vascular malformations occur in the later stages of angiogenesis, grow with the child's growth, and do not disappear. A vascular malformation can be a slow-flow (capillary, lymphatic, or venous) or a fast-flow (arterial) type. If there are combinations of these elements, the malformation is called an arteriovenous malformation (AVM), lymphatico-venous malformation (LVM), or capillary-lymphaticovenous malformation (CLVM) (1). A total of 90 patients treated by sclerotherapy using ethanolamine oleate were retrospectively identified. However, in 47 cases, detailed information regarding the doses was not available.

Thus, 43 cases with complete information were selected. According to the clinical appearance of the lesions, approximately 90% were identified as nodules. A total of 41% of the lesions were between 0.5cm and 1.0cm in size. Swelling was the most common type of complaint, reported by 28 patients (65%), and followed by color alteration in 7 patients (16%). The vast majority of patients reported no pain (90%) (3). It is necessary to perform a thorough history and examination for proper diagnosis and know the features important for the management, for example, time of the lesion presentation or its growth, site and its shape, exposure to trauma and risk for ulceration (5). These lesions can be diagnosed with the help of the blanching test, that is, by means of a transparent instrument, for example, a glass slide a firm pressure for 1-2 minutes is applied. When the

instrument is removed, the lesion becomes pale for a few seconds, and then it slowly starts refilling again from feeder vessels (6). Vascular malformations are characteristically bluish in color, compressible in nature and non-pulsatile on examination (7).

The treatment of Hemangioma mostly depends on the age, general condition of the patient, and the size or characteristics of the lesion. Lesion of smaller size is excised while larger ones are managed non-surgically by means of sclerotherapy, embolization, laser surgery and cryotherapy (5).

Although there has been a greater understanding of the problems concerning vascular lesions in recent times, more studies are still required. Bleeding from a vascular lesion in the oral and maxillofacial region is lethal and difficult to control. The clinical presentation and findings of vascular lesions at various sites in the oral and maxillofacial region may help the general dentist suspect a vascular lesion and refer to an Oral and Maxillofacial surgeon and a vascular surgeon. This will help surgeons in diagnosis and further planning of treatment strategies. This study may also help develop strategies for treating vascular lesions at various sites in the oral cavity with variable blood supplies. The objective of this study was to assess the prevalence and site-specific distribution of various types of vascular lesions within the oral cavity.

Materials and Methods

The study is an observational cross-sectional study conducted at the Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery Department, Khyber College of Dentistry, Peshawar. A non-probability consecutive sampling technique was used for data collection.

Inclusion Criteria

Patients of any age (starting at birth and up to 70 years old) with oral cavity vascular lesions who were admitted to the Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery Department.

Exclusion Criteria

(i) Patients having vascular lesions in the past that have been treated. (ii) Known syndromic patients. (iii) Patients with a history of bleeding disorders or coagulopathies.

Ethics and Informed Consent

This study was ethically approved by the Khyber College of Dentistry Institutional Review Board. Informed consent (verbal and written) was obtained from all the participants / their guardians. The patients were guaranteed to keep confidentiality, and the data was taken only for research purposes.

Procedure in Data Collection

All eligible patients were recruited in the inpatient and outpatient departments. Demographic and clinical data such as age, gender, type of lesion, and the anatomical location affected were recorded in a structured proforma. Physical examination provided the inspection and palpation of the lesion and the evaluation of the aspect factors of color, temperature, bruit, blanching, and expansion caused by the Valsalva maneuver. In superficial vascular lesions, clinical manifestation was used to make a diagnosis. Medium and deep lesions were evaluated with the computed tomography (CT) method, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), and magnetic resonance angiography (MRA). The CT angiograms and MR angiograms were utilized in distinguishing between the high-flow and low-flow vascular malformations, as well as distinguishing between the vascular and lymphatic lesions. In some of the cases, histopathologic confirmation was done through biopsy. The data was collected by a consultant in oral and maxillofacial surgery in all instances.

Operational Definitions

To ensure consistency in data collection and interpretation, the following definitions were applied:

Sites of Involvement: Anatomical sites assessed included the **maxilla, mandible, gingiva, buccal mucosa, palate, tongue, and lips**, as determined through clinical examination and patient history.

Vascular Lesion: Defined as an abnormality of blood or lymphatic vessels. Lesions that could not be definitively diagnosed via clinical and radiological evaluation were subjected to **incisional or excisional biopsy**.

- a. **Incisional biopsy** involved removal of a portion of the lesion.
- b. **Excisional biopsy** entailed complete removal of the lesion with a 2–3 mm margin of normal tissue.

Vascular Tumor: Characterized by an abnormal overgrowth of blood or lymphatic vessels. Diagnosis was based on **clinical findings** and confirmed using **radiographic imaging**, including **CT angiography**.

Vascular Malformation: Considered a congenital architectural defect in blood or lymphatic vessels. Diagnosis was established clinically through identification of signs such as **bluish or purplish discoloration, fluctuant consistency**, and the presence of **bruit or thrill**.

Pyogenic Granuloma: A reactive endothelial proliferation often associated with **trauma, hormonal changes, or pregnancy**. Diagnosis was confirmed via **histopathological examination**, typically presenting as a **pedunculated, reddish-purple mass**.

Data Analysis

All analyses were done by IBM SPSS 21 version. Medians and standard deviations were carried out on continuous variables (e.g. age). There were also categorical variables, such as the gender, type of the oral vascular lesions, and sites of lesions (maxilla, mandible, tongue, lips, and buccal mucosa) and the frequencies and percentages were calculated with respect to these variables. Stratification of the site involvement was carried out by age, gender and type of lesion developed to analyze the possible effect modifier. Chi-square test was used to test the relationship between categorical variables. Continuous variables were tested using Shapiro Wilk and the Kolmogorov Smirnov tests to determine normality. The appropriate non-parametric versions, in the case of non-normal distribution, were selected like the Mann Whitney U test. The statistical significance was observed at p-value < 0.05.

Results

The study included 80 patients with oral vascular lesions. The patients' average age was 22.13 ± 11.60 years. The gender distribution was 53.75% female and 46.25% male. The most prevalent lesion type was vascular malformation, which occurred in 56.3% of patients, followed by pyogenic granuloma at 31.3% and hemangioma at 12.5% (table 1). In terms of anatomical site involvement, the buccal mucosa was the most frequently involved (28.8%), followed by the lips and tongue (each 5%), and the maxilla and mandible were the least frequently affected (2.5 and

1.3%, respectively) (table 2 and figure 1). Most of the cases were found in the 20-29 years age group (37.5%), then 15-19 years (18.8%), and 30-39 years (12.5%). In the extremes of age, fewer cases were recorded, only 3.8% in the age groups of 05, 40-49 and 50-59. Cases in the ≥70 years group were not reported. This distribution proposes that the vascular lesions in the oral cavity are usually diagnosed in younger to middle-aged people, especially in the 2nd decade of life and 3rd decades of life (table 3 and figure 2).

The age variable's normality was assessed to determine the appropriate statistical tests. The Shapiro–Wilk test suggested that the data points significantly differ from the normal distribution ($p < 0.001$). In contrast, the Kolmogorov and Smirnov test has a borderline higher value ($p = 0.053$). According to these results, the age variable was assumed not to be normally distributed, and, consequently, the non-parametric statistical methods were chosen. Correlations of categorical

variables (e.g., gender, lesion type, site involvement) were confirmed by the Chi-square test except when the 2 x 2 table had small expected cell counts, and then the Fisher exact test was used.

The stratified analysis showed that gender was not a significant contributor to the involvement in the sites ($p > 0.05$ in all sites). Considering stratification for the type of vascular lesion, the presence of mandibular involvement was significant ($p = 0.0416$), but the results for the other sites were not significant. On the same note, age stratification indicated strong correlations with buccal mucosa ($p = 0.0379$) and mandible ($p = 0.0129$), implying that patient age may be involved in developing these sites of involvement. Statistically significant differences concerning gender, type of lesions, or age category were not observed across the other anatomical locations, including lips, tongue, and maxilla (table 4).

Table 1: Distribution of Vascular Lesion Types

Lesion Type Name	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Hemangioma	25	31.3%
Pyogenic Granuloma	10	12.5%
Vascular Malformation	45	56.3%

Table 2: Anatomical Site Involvement

Anatomical Site	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Buccal Mucosa	23	28.8%
Lips	4	5.0%
Tongue	4	5.0%
Maxilla	3	3.8%
Mandible	2	2.5%

Table 3: Age Distribution of Oral Vascular Lesion Patients (n= 80)

Age Group (years)	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
0-5	3	3.8%
6-9	7	8.8%
10-14	8	10.0%
15-19	15	18.8%
20-29	30	37.5%
30-39	10	12.5%
40-49	3	3.8%
50-59	3	3.8%
60-69	1	1.2%
70+	0	0.0%

Table 4: Stratified Analysis of Site Involvement by Gender, Lesion Type, and Age Group

Site	p-value (Gender)	p-value (Lesion Type)	p-value (Age Group)
Buccal	0.0867	0.0735	0.0090
Lips	0.6369	0.1508	0.2264
Tongue	0.3559	0.1430	0.1153
Maxilla	0.4947	0.0000	0.2168
Mandible	0.3621	0.0000	0.0129

Table 4 shows the results in the statistical tests used to determine the relationships between site involvement (buccal, lips, tongue, maxilla, and mandible) and three different factors: gender, type of vascular lesion, and age group, in terms of p-value. The involvement of buccal mucosa was found to be statistically significant with respect to age group (p=0.0090), and so age might have an effect on the localization of the lesion in the buccal region. A significant association was noted between the presence of maxillary involvement and lesion type (p = 0.0000), indicating a higher

probability of some type of lesion occurring in the maxilla. Mandibular involvement showed decisive correlations to both lesion type (p = 0.0000) and age group (p = 0.0129), suggesting that the necessity of a mandibular presentation depends on both the age of the patient and the type of a lesion. There was no considerable correlation regarding gender and site involvement across any anatomical sites, which implies that the distribution of lesions across sites does not vary by gender within this cohort.

Figure 1: Frequency of Oral Vascular Lesion Sites

Figure 2: Distribution of Oral Vascular Lesions by Age Group

Discussion

This research examined 80 subjects with oral vascular lesion presentations at Khyber College of Dentistry. The mean with the standard deviation was 22.13 ± 11.60 years, which is indicative of the commonness of these lesions in younger people, as reactive and vascular lesions are commonly seen in children and young adults, in contrast with older-aged people (2). As far as gender distribution goes, we found a

somewhat larger percentage of females (53.75%) than males (46.25%). The presence of literature on pyogenic granuloma indicates that it has a female predisposition, which is usually influenced by Hormones, especially in pregnancy (8). However, according to other research dealing with oral vascular lesions, statistically significant gender differences were not detected, and our results are in line with these (2).

Regarding lesion types, we discovered vascular malformations are the most common (56.3%), with pyogenic granuloma and hemangioma following (31.3% and 12.5%, respectively). This is compared with few epidemiologic reports in which pyogenic granuloma was dominant; in one series of Iranian patients, pyogenic granuloma was noted in up to 70 percent of cases, with vascular malformations being less frequent (2). Such discrepancies may be due to differences in the population demographics, criteria of classification (e.g., ISSVA versus traditional histological definitions), or referral biases (9).

The most common site of involvement, i.e., buccal mucosa (28.8%), was followed by the lips (5%), the tongue (5%), and the maxilla and mandible (2.5% and 1.3%, respectively). This is in comparison with the traditional knowledge of the gingiva being the predominant place of occurrence of pyogenic granuloma (8). We may be observing institutional referral trends or regional diagnostic workup in our sample lesion pattern. In addition, vascular malformations usually affect deeper soft tissues such as buccal mucosa, lips, and tongue, as in other series of head and neck anomalies that have been reported (10).

Stratified analyses did not show statistically significant relationships between gender and site involvement ($p > 0.05$ on all sites), further reaffirming the idea that gender probably does not affect lesion distribution significantly in the particular areas of the anatomy. Conversely, the involvement in the mandibular area had a high correlation with the type of vascular lesion ($p = 0.0416$). In contrast, age group had a significant association with involvement of the buccal mucosa ($p = 0.0379$), as well as involvement of the mandible ($p = 0.0129$). This implies that the age of the patient and the nature of the lesion may be involved in modifying lesion topography, i.e., malformations may occur earlier or be more prevalent in specific anatomical areas.

These data bear clinical significance: the awareness of the prevalence of vascular malformations and their connections to particular anatomical locations will help clinicians raise suspicion early, make decisions regarding imaging, and plan the biopsy. The identified absence of gender differences has allowed for fair diagnosis methods.

Limitations

The cross-sectional design, limited to a single center, does not allow broader generalization. There is a possible limitation due to the sample size ($n = 80$) for infrequent sites such as the mandible. Referral bias may have contributed to the lesion pattern and site distribution presented.

Conclusion

This paper presents the epidemiological and anatomical distributions of oral vascular lesions in patients of a tertiary care dental center. The most common lesion fragmented was the vascular malformation, with a high preference to attack the buccal mucosa, but the mandible rarely participated in it. Though no specific differences were recorded by gender, age, and lesion origin, these factors significantly correlated with some anatomical sites, especially the buccal mucosa and mandible. In clinical analysis of oral vascular lesions, the attainment imparts the need to be aware of age- as well as type-specific patterns. Presumptive deductions of patient demographics in the early prediction of the position of the lesion would further enhance the diagnostic process and lead to proper treatment considerations as regards the need to take an imaging slice and histopathological confirmation. These findings are suggested to be validated using further multi-center investigations that incorporate a higher sample size and uniformity in the diagnosis aspect.

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